

REVISITING AMBEDKAR'S VIEW ON THE CASTE SYSTEM WITH SPECIAL
REFERENCE TO DISCRIMINATION AND FREEDOM

* Dr. Bikash Mondal

Abstract:

B.R. Ambedkar, an exponent of socio-political-religious revolution, reshaped Indian social consciousness and restructured Indian social order, which are critically examined through a unique lens that challenges traditional orthodox philosophies. For Ambedkar, the central issue with these orthodox philosophies is casteism. There are several reasons Why Ambedkar considers casteism to be so problematic. Herein, I will explore two major reasons: the presence of discrimination and the lack of individual freedom.

Ambedkar believes that freedom is crucial in the fight against all forms of discrimination. When individuals experience true freedom, they can redefine their purpose and meaning in life. Therefore, eliminating discrimination and safeguarding individual freedom are essential steps that Ambedkar identifies for creating a just society. In the first section, I shall explain why Ambedkar considers the caste system to be a discriminatory social order. In the second section, I will also explore why he believes the caste system infringes upon individual freedom.

Key Words: *Caste System, Hierarchy, Freedom, Discrimination, Social Order*

Assistant Professor, Department of Philosophy, West Bengal State University

B. R. Ambedkar's idea of the caste system as a discriminatory social system

B.R. Ambedkar upholds the Caste System, which is an idea which involves discrimination because it promotes such a social stratification through which it tries to subjugate different individuals' rights. As Ambedkar puts it, "Inside the community there is no discrimination among those who are recognized as kindred bound by kinship. The community recognizes that everyone within it is entitled to all the rights equally with others. (Rodrigues 231). Ambedkar hints herein that the caste system creates such a community within which people are not kindred because it allows the idea of gradation that is hierarchical in nature. And all gradations are yet to be bound by the value of kinship; this gradation is more often guided by the concept of superiority. As he further (1990) puts, "The Caste System is not merely a division of labourers which is quite different from division of labour—it is a hierarchy in which the division of labourers are graded one above the another" (47). This gradation does not divide the works of individuals, nor does the gradation need to prefer the performances of labourers; rather, this gradation prefers only the labourers' social position determined by

their birth, which the Hindu religion endorsed, and, unfortunately, humans could not change their social gradations by choosing such an occupation that the Hindu religion did not authorise. This means a socio-religious force restricts people from changing their socially recognised activities. What would be the problem if this structure denied accepting any changes? Ambedkar believes the values imposed on every gradation may create a big issue when considering a group of people as higher or superior and others as lower or inferior based on their birth positions.

This value-oriented graded system is perhaps to be considered antagonistic to the idea of equality of rights because what advantages and disadvantages would be provided to individuals is firmly determined by their hierarchical social position. Individual potentials and efficacies had not been recognised in the distribution of labour in the caste system. As Ambedkar puts it, "This division of labour is not spontaneous; it is not based on natural aptitudes. Social and individuals' efficiency requires us to develop the capacity of an individual to the point of competency to choose and to make his own career" (Rodrigues 263). But Ambedkar considers that this principle is

violated in the caste system when this system provides tasks to individuals not considering their propensities, but considering their socio-religious-hierarchical positions. This sort of socio-religious prescription of Hinduism is one that an individual cannot deny for their well-being. Moreover, the prescriptions are not the same for those who belong to the Hindu society. Every grade has specific duties, and some duties are recognised as superior and others are inferior. This is so unfortunate that a superior social position is confined by birth, for which individuals had no choice. Individuals' propensity and their capability do not determine what their socio-political religious position would be. This is obviously a form of discrimination; discrimination is such a concept that encompasses the idea of deprivation, without which the connotation of discrimination just refers to the idea of separation. But discrimination is not merely similar to a separation. The idea of discrimination in the context of the socio-political and religious realm bears the idea of segregation and deprivation. An international treatise tries to understand the meaning of discrimination in terms of deprivation. As Altman and Andrew (2020) put it,

In his review of the international treaties that outlaw discrimination, Wouter Vandenberg finds that [t]here is no universally accepted definition of discrimination' (2005: 33). The core human rights documents fail to define discrimination at all, simply providing non-exhaustive lists of the grounds on which discrimination is to be prohibited. Thus, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights declares that "the law shall prohibit any discrimination and guarantee to all persons equal and effective protection against discrimination on any ground such as race, color, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status (Article 26). (Para 2)

It follows that discrimination in terms of deprivation, based on colour, race, gender, or ethnicity, is to be legally prohibited. We may also say that to deprive someone of something else is, in a broader sense, considering him as a means. Individuals should not be treated as means but as ends in themselves. Ambedkar, like Kant, believes the individual man is a free and autonomous being. As he puts it, "The first [condition of free social order] is that

the individual is an end in himself and that the aim and object of society is the growth of the individual and the development of his personality. Society is not above the individual and if the individual has to subordinate himself to society, it is because such subordination is for his betterment and only to the extent necessary. (Writing and Speeches, Vol. 3. 95).

Ambedkar herein carries a liberalistic attitude and opens the issue of individuals' subordination into the context of society as he prioritises individuals over society. It follows, for the common interest, that individual interest should not be perished. Individuals are not the means for societal progress, but rather society is a means for the well-being of individuals. Although Ambedkar further believes some differences are natural among individuals: colour, height, propensity, strength, etc., they are equal in the sense of possessing "moral equality". As he quotes professor Beard from his essay on "Freedom in Political Thought", "It is easy to point out inequalities in physical strength, in artistic skill, in material wealth or in mental capacity . . . At the end it remains a fact that fundamental characteristics appear in all human beings. Their nature and manifestations are

summed up in the phrase 'moral equality'." (Writing and Speeches, vol. 3. 96-97). This means humans are equal for moral consideration; from moral perspective, individuals should be treated as equal. As Ambedkar puts it, "The inferiority complex of the Untouchable is the result of their isolation, discrimination and the unfriendliness of the social environment (Rodrigues 235). It implies that social structure invokes a non-reciprocal social relationship. Ambedkar perhaps here argues for a reciprocal relationship based on kinship. In this regard, Ambedkar raises many questions against the Hindu-social behaviour towards Untouchables. The most pertinent question is, as Ambedkar puts it, "Does it [Hinduism] teach the Hindus that the Untouchables are their kindred? He cannot find any positive answer within Hinduism and he argues that Untouchables are the stakeholder of Hinduism, yet enlightened people deny acknowledging untouchables as their kindred. . . (Rodrigues 228). Again, he puts it, "Untouchability is a part of Hinduism. Even those who for the sake of posing as enlightened reformers deny that untouchability is a part of Hinduism are found to observe untouchability (Rodrigues .229)." He found

the cause of practicing untouchability is to maintain the consciousness of superiority. As he puts, "It [Hindu] enhances his sense of superiority by the reason of this consciousness that millions of untouchables [are] below him" (Rodrigues 229). The idea of superiority perhaps presupposes the idea of subordination. Those who are considered superior often try to subordinate inferiors. It implies that the Hindu-social order denies the principles of the state of nature. It believes in equality and denies any kind of subordination; here, all are under the guidance of natural law. As Locke (1824) puts, "The State of Nature has a law of nature to govern it, which obliges every one, and reason, which is that law, teaches all mankind who will but consult it, that being all equal and independent in his life, health, liberty or possession;" (133). From this statement, it is clear enough that "The State of Nature" is an equal state of affairs where everyone is considered as equal; no one will lose their liberty, life, health and possession for the sake of society or of a community. Above all, there is no power structure in "The State of Nature"; all are being treated as equal, and those who belong to that state maintain a reciprocal relationship; none sets one above another. As Locke (1824) puts

again, "A State also of equality, wherein all power and jurisdiction are reciprocal, no one having more than another, there being nothing more evident than that creates of same species and rank, promiscuously born to all the same advantages of nature, and the use of the same faculty..." (132). In "The State of Nature", the graded and non-reciprocal relationships were not allowed, and the advantages of nature are to be shared by all equally. This state permits no hierarchical structure, but the caste system as an essential part of Hinduism, unlike "The State of Nature" used to rank one above another. The fallout of the caste system makes some individuals ready to perish for the sake of society in a negative sense. So, the caste system fails to adopt the principle of equality; rather, it allows a graded inequality.

What sort of inequality is it? All grades do not have equal rights in the caste system. This system is used to treat top-graded people as superior and lower-graded people as inferior. Moreover, this gradation determines the advantages and disadvantages in terms of the rights of the individuals belonging to that system. Now the question is, how far will we accept this structure rationally? If this structure does

not follow the principle of subordination and adopts the principle of equal opportunity for all individuals to access the elevated dais irrespective of their socio-religious identities, we will perhaps have no problem accepting this structure because then it will be open to all, and it will more satisfy the principle of equality. If the structure is guided by the principle of equality, the notion of subordination will lose its scope. Although all forms of subordination are invariably constructed, all forms of subordination might not be implemented in a negative sense. But the form of subordination practised in the caste system is obviously vicious because this form of subordination undermines the values of kinship and promotes the notion of social deprivation. For the eradication of social deprivation, Ambedkar chose kinship as an alternative for the protection of marginalised people. As he puts it, "Kinship with another community is the best insurance which the Untouchables can affect against Hindu tyranny and Hindu oppression." (Rodrigues 232). He believes kinship (within a community) may not open the ground for discrimination, but within the Hindu community, he found the absence of kinship with Untouchables. He further

believes that the presence of kinship denies the notion of deprivation as well as discrimination. This is the reason why he tried to discard caste-based hierarchy based on deprivation/ oppression against the marginalised section of people.

I, so far, have tried to explain how the notion of the caste system involves discrimination in terms of promoting deprivation. Further questions will be raised about the deprivation of what? Ambedkar considers deprivation of freedom in terms of different rights. Now, I will try to explore how the notion of the caste system infringes on individuals' freedom.

B. R. Ambedkar's view on individual freedom

Ambedkar considers associated living as freedom and non-associated living as a barrier to individuals' freedom because he believes rights in terms of freedom are secured by associated living. He also believes that associated living must be founded on liberty. On the other hand, he believes non-associated living is firmly founded on deprivation of freedom. It means, for him, social intercourse and social-fellow feeling within the community members are the necessary conditions of denying deprivation

and accepting freedom of others, and non-associated living is diametrically opposite to it because it invokes external coercion to deny individuals' liberty. As he puts it, "The second essential [condition for a free society] is that the terms of associated life between members of society must be regarded by consideration founded on liberty, equality and fraternity" (Writing and Speeches, vol.3, 95). Here, Ambedkar considers three essential principles for associate living: liberty, equality and fraternity. Now, I mainly explore the liberty aspect of associated living. For him, liberty means to remove or obliterate socio-political-religious barriers that are indicative of negative freedom. As Berlin (1969) defines negative liberty, "I am normally said to be free to the degree to which no man or body of men interferences with my activity. Political liberty in this sense is simply the area within which a man can act unobstructed by others." (15-16). Although Berlin defines negative freedom in the context of politics, it may apply in every sector of human life. For him, all sorts of coercion are not subject to questioning. But the coercion, deliberately made against humans for depriving something else which are needed for the rational choices of

human beings, is to be questioned. As he puts it, "coercion implies the deliberate interference of other human beings within the area in which I could otherwise act" (Berlin 16). The implication is that what a human deserves is denied to fulfil the interests of others. Similarly, Ambedkar tries to remove initially external religious coercions, which are the foe of freedom of conscience, made against mainly the depressed class, for protecting their freedom of association. This freedom Rawls considers as the third basic liberty. It means it is necessary for rational human choices. The implication is that liberty seems to be considered the most valuable object to fulfil human purposes in life. Freeman explores the Rawlsian idea of the freedom of association. He says that this freedom goes parallel with the freedom of conscience because without religious conviction has at minimum value (Freeman 48). Similarly, Ambedkar argues for associated living for the depressed class with other communities or groups that existed in India. As Ambedkar (1990) puts it, "The strength of a society depends upon the presence of points of contact, possibilities of interaction between different groups which exist in it" (71). So, we could infer that when Ambedkar

talks about associated living, he firmly advocates for the freedom of association and the freedom of conscience as well. He firmly considers the caste institution as a form of violation of associated living. As Ambedkar further puts it, “No wonder individual Hindus have not had the courage to assert their independence by breaking the barriers of caste.” (Rodrigues 274). Caste institution, as an external coercion, believes in the concept of otherness, although the others are part of this institution. A disassociation of marginalised people creates a feeling of isolation that indicates such a social structure, which promotes recognised hatred and the lack of kinship. However, the antonym of associated living is perhaps isolation. As Ambedkar puts it (Rodrigues 233), “Isolation means social segregation, social humiliation, social discrimination and social injustice. . . Isolation means want of sympathy, want of fellowship and want of consideration. . . Isolation means positive hatred and antipathy from the Hindus.” This statement refers to Berlin’s account of negative liberty; the absence of this liberty is perhaps an obstacle to associated living. A question herein might be raised about what the consequences of this isolation are. This isolation prepares the ground for the

infringement of different sorts of Individuals' freedom. Now I try to explore the infringement of Socio-political and economic freedom for those who belong to the caste system.

Socio-political freedom

I have already hinted that the caste system more often denies the socio-religious rights of some people within the same homogeneous group. This sort of denial of socio-religious rights leads them towards the denial, preparing the ground for the infringement of freedom. For Individuals, freedom is more important for necessary planning for future life because without freedom, individuals might not diligently survive. But the socio-religious conditions of the caste system create such a situation that appears as an external coercion for which so-called lower-grade people cannot give values on their lives, as freedom is regarded as the fundamental condition of valuable life. Amartya Sen also considers freedom as a valuable thing for the rational choices of human life. As Amartya Sen (2009) believes,

Freedom is valuable for at least two different reasons. First, more freedom gives us our objectives – that thing that we value. It helps, for example, in our ability to decide to live as we would like

and to promote the ends that we may want to advance. This aspect of freedom is concerned with our ability to achieve what we value, no matter what the process is through which that achievement comes about. Second, we may attach importance to the *process* of choice itself. We may, for example want to make sure that we are not being forced into some state because of constraints imposed by others. The distinction between the 'opportunity aspect' and the process aspect of freedom can be both significant and quite far-reaching. (228)

The process aspect of freedom concerns individuals who have taken such a means through which they want to pursue what they would like to plan for their future life, and the opportunity aspect of freedom is to be defined in terms of the availability of opportunities to individuals for choosing one of them. The confinement of opportunity seems to be treated as a violation of individuals' freedom simply because they have no option to choose favourable ones for fulfilling their interests. Individuals, in this context, are bound to choose what has been accorded. On the other hand, the process aspect of freedom is

to be violated due to authoritarianism. According to Sen, one person decides to go outside and thinks about how to go there, but the authority of society has also decided to confine that person from going there. It is a violation of individual freedom in terms of the means that she adopts for the exercise of her freedom. I may argue that there will be no distinctive place for violation of the process aspect of freedom in the caste system because people had not enjoyed the freedom to do what they actually want to do. It does not mean that people have no concern about their plans; rather, people have a lot of goals in life to achieve, but how they can fulfil their interests is restricted. He could think about the planning of his life following their will, but due to societal conditions, they are unable to fulfil their interests. It is such an antithetical view of the individual's free will. This sort of social restriction imposed upon individuals indicates the violation of the social freedom of individuals. As Ambedkar (1990) ascertained, "It is found where, as in the Caste System, some persons are compelled to carry on certain prescribed callings which are not of their choice" (65). This statement clearly shows that individuals who belonged to the caste

system had no social freedom at all, even if the so-called higher-caste people could not deny the prescription of the caste system. Now, we can take the opportunity aspect of freedom into account. According to such an aspect of freedom, people are perhaps free to choose one from many alternatives. A necessary question is to be raised here as to whether there are available alternatives for individuals to choose from in the caste system. As Ambedkar (1990) put it, "The division of labour brought about by caste is not a division based on choice. Individual sentiment, individual preferences had no place in it" (47). If we analyse the concept of choice, the notion of alternative derived from it as any "choice" is not made possible without having the idea of an alternative. That is to say, the choice would be feasible while many more alternatives are available for choosing one of them. The concept of choice has directly involved the notion of freedom. In the context of the caste system, the problem of choice is prevalent in that it cannot offer many more alternatives to people who belong to that system. So, I may say that the opportunity aspect of freedom is hardly recognised in the caste system. In addition to it, I may further categorise the idea of opportunity into two distinct forms:

the privileged opportunity and the non-privileged opportunity. By the privileged opportunity, I mean the opportunity related to social prestige. That is to say, some activities that are socially recognised as prestigious are not open to all. This sort of opportunity was denied to the lower-graded people in the caste-based hierarchical system. The people who occupied a top grade used to have the privilege of this sort of opportunity. On the other hand, by the non-privileged opportunity, I mean the opportunity that does not have any social prestige at all. Some activities performed by the so-called lower-grade people are still not being deemed as prestigious. The opportunity to perform non-prestigious social services was confined to so-called lower-grade people. A question may arise as to how the caste system confines an individual's privileged opportunity aspect of freedom. The caste system, time and again, violates the principle of equality as it does not allow an egalitarian concept of justice. As Ambedkar (1990) put it, "The objection to equality may be sound and one may have to admit that all men are not equal. But what of that? Equality may be a fiction but nonetheless one must accept it as the governing principle" (65). In this statement,

Ambedkar tries to distinguish natural inequalities among individuals from the inequalities prescribed by social institutions. There are a lot of natural differences among individuals, but they should not be treated unequally. The Hindu social structure more often than not treats lower-graded people unequally, following the principle of caste structure: the lower-graded people should serve the higher-graded people without having privileged opportunities. It is basically a form of authoritarianism because, in the caste system, people are not to be guided by what they like to do but by what the orthodox Hindu authority likes. According to this authority, people in the caste system are not to be treated as equals, having privileged opportunities. That is the reason why the privileged opportunities for the well-being of some lower-grade people were being restricted, viz., the opportunity of education and performing the religious rites and rituals were not accessible to the *Shudras*, Untouchables. So, the people who belong to the lower grade are deprived of having equal-social freedom that is needed to maintain a prestigious social life. Although they also have the capacity to be recognised as autonomous by virtue of moral agency, the caste system does not

recognise individuals' autonomy, as Kant mentioned. They should have received equal treatment by virtue of their autonomy, but they would have failed to receive such equal treatment because of caste-based institutional obligations. Moreover, the caste system more often than not tries to close the door of opportunity for a specified group of people. Thus, the caste system allows us to consider it an unequal social system because it infringes on almost all social rights of downtrodden individuals. Moreover, he believes that social democracy (truly participation in social activities) is the pedestal of political and economic justice because without kinship we cannot accept others' political and economic rights; for him, social bondage seems to be the precondition of the success of political as well as economic democracy.

Along with social liberty, Ambedkar considers political liberty has also a vital role for making democracy vibrant in a true sense (actual sharing of power among every predicament of society) because he believes that the idea of freedom of contract is such an erroneous ideology for which parliamentary democracy failed. As he puts,

Of the erroneous ideologies which have been responsible for the failure of parliamentary democracy, I have no doubt that the idea of freedom of contract is one of them. The idea became sanctified and was upheld in the name of liberty. Parliamentary democracy took no notice of economic inequalities and did not care to examine the result of freedom of contract on the parties to the contract. In spite of the fact they were unequal in their bargaining power. (Rodrigues 62)

To protect equal participation for every section of society, Ambedkar tries to ensure equal representation from every segment of Indian society in bargaining for political power. Equal participation might guarantee equal political agreement. Due to the lack of participation in the process of democracy, the majority of people could not realise real political freedom, for which Ambedkar blamed the wrong organisation. As he puts it, "All political societies get divided into two classes—the Rulers and the Ruled. . . . But the unfortunate part of it is that the division becomes so stereotyped and stratified that Rulers are always drawn from the ruling class and the class is ruled never

becomes the ruling class" (Rodrigues 62). Herein Ambedkar hints that "hereditary ruling class" is always ruling over servile class by manipulating organization. They perhaps participate in the process of democracy for retaining their power position, i.e., some people who are coming from a monarchical family participated in the parliamentary process of democracy were able to capture their previous political supremacy, become chief ministers and other forms of ministers to rule over the servile class. As Ambedkar puts it, ". . . adult suffrage and frequent election are no bar against governing class reaching places of powers and authority" (Rodrigues 63). According to him, due to an inferiority complex, the servile class consider "the member of ruling class as their natural leader and servile class them volunteer to elect members of the governing class as their rulers". (Rodrigues 63). This is the reason why he argues not only for adult suffrage but also for the right to representation by the constitution. If we are unable to do that, the emancipation will never be possible. As he puts it, ". . . the political emancipation of unenfranchised will be entirely at the mercy of those that are enfranchised." (Rodrigues 65). By

providing the Indian constitution as a device to protect real political freedom of the masses, Ambedkar tries to stabilise and integrate Indian society. As he puts it, ". . . the principal aim of such a constitution must be to dislodge the governing class from its position and to prevent it from remaining as a governing class for ever. . ."(Rodrigues 64).

His idea of democracy is today so pertinent because this idea can prevent the unrest situation in the present world. The most parts of the world have recently faced such a problem that is perhaps rooted in the lack of real political freedom or democracy. Ambedkar's idea of democracy can give new hope to countries facing problems of democracy.

The absence of socio-political liberty breeds economic injustice or the lack of economic freedom. Now I will focus on economic liberty—

Economic Liberty

Let me try to explore what shot of economic liberty or justice Ambedkar desires. Ambedkar believes that the economic right is compatible with a socialistic-democratic framework. His prescribed economic right seems not to be treated as just negative liberty. It is a

positive self-respect and self-direction towards the ends of human life without institutional coercion. As he (1990) puts it, "... the Caste System will not allow Hindus to take to occupations where they are wanted if they do not belong to them by heredity. If a Hindu is seen to starve rather than take to new occupations not assigned to his Caste, the reason is to be found in the Caste System (48). The caste system, as an external coercion, denies economic participation and gives no freedom to choose careers over the prescriptions of the caste institution. The restricted stratification of occupation may make individuals jobless. As Ambedkar (1990) asserted,

Look at from another point of view this stratification of occupations which is the result of the caste system is positively pernicious. Industry is never static. It undergoes rapid and abrupt changes. With such changes an individual must be free to change his occupation. Without such freedom to adjust himself to changing circumstances it would be impossible to gain his livelihood. (p.48)

What Ambedkar says might be interpreted as a liberal economic approach, as he argues herein for the autonomy of individuals to choose and

change their occupation. Liberal societies respect individual choices and tolerate different socio-religious and philosophical views (Freeman, 44). The lack of this liberty is a corollary of disassociated living. This is the reason why Ambedkar argues for associated living for the untouchable with the entire Hindu community.

Conclusion

Engaged in this research, I have tried to explore how the caste system, as advocated by Ambedkar, involves in promoting discrimination and infringes different kinds of individuals' freedom. Throughout this work, I have tried to evaluate the concept of caste system and observed the notion of the caste system, which is a discriminatory social order that has given a minimum scope of individual socio-religious rights, on account of their caste identity, to the so-called lower-graded people. I have also observed that the two aspects of freedom, as Prof Sen analysed, are denied in the caste system. The graded people, in the caste system, cannot avail the process aspects of freedom because the opportunity of freedom institutionally is closed to them. Here, I try to argue that

all sorts of opportunities were not closed, but some privileged opportunities to lower-graded people were denied, while non-privileged opportunities were available for them. These opportunities, given to them, are not treated as a matter of choice; rather, they were bound to choose these opportunities. The caste system, however, deliberately imposed authoritarian principles upon the so-called lower-graded people. Moreover, the autonomy is restricted for the concretisation of individuals' freedom.

I have also notice that Ambedkar mainly focus on three types of freedom: social, political and economic freedom. His idea of social freedom is the foundation of political and economic freedom. His idea of economic freedom is based on liberalism but cannot deny socialistic framework. And his notion of political freedom is satisfying the true democratic values: equal participation of very predicament of the society. This value can resolve the unrest situation faced by the people of many different countries.

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